

Research Article

Attitudes and Perceptions of the Emirates Women Towards Facial Skin Care Products and Herbal Cosmetics

Heyam Ali¹, Rasha Saad², Ahmed Ahmed³, Babiker El-Haj⁴

¹Department of Pharmaceutics and Pharmacy Practice, Dubai Pharmacy college Dubai, United Arab Emirates

²Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, School of Pharmacy, Management & Science University, Malaysia

³General surgery-Colorectal department, Nottingham Hospital, United Kingdom,

⁴Ajman University of Science and Technology, Sh. riqah, United Arab Emirates.

Available Online: 1st May, 2015

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study were: To examine Attitudes and behaviour of emirates women related to facial skin care products. To discover the similarities and differences in the Attitudes and behaviour of young and middle-aged women when using these products. and to discover what kind of attitudes of emirates women have towards facial skin care products containing natural ingredients. The study was conducted by using quantitative research method. Data was collected through a designed questionnaire and was distributed by conducting an email survey or distribution to customers in shopping centers & pharmacies in different districts in United Arab Emirates (Dubai, Sharjah, Fujairah, Ras-Keimah and Abu-Dubai). The questionnaire was designed addressing women who are young (20 to 35) and middle-aged (40 to 50) years old women. All together, 138 women who fit the two age categories, in this study. Only 100 responded and answered the research questionnaire. The results indicated that women in the two age categories were rather similar in terms of attitudes and behaviour related to facial skin care products. However, some differences were also found for example in the decision-making process. Regarding the attitudes toward the use of natural ingredients in facial skin care products, differences were found between different demographic groups. For example, women who had children were more favorable toward the use of natural ingredients than women who did not have children. In sum, the objectives of this study were met well. Although existing literature suggests that factors such as age, education & financial status have an impact on attitudes and behaviour, toward the use of facial skin care products & the herbal ones. The results showed that it does not have that big impact. However, these findings of this study can definitely benefit the case companies of skin care products in UAE in their business actions.

Key words: Emirates women, Attitudes and behaviour, facial skin care products, herbal cosmetics.

INTRODUCTION

Beauty and skin care products are no longer only for the women nowadays; men also are increasingly using the skin care products. Beauty & skin care products are now social obsessions across age, gender and race worldwide^[1]. People are becoming Beauty conscious and want to satisfy the need to look and feel good^[2]. In addition to that, skin and beauty care products used for medical reasons in different shape and patterns including for example, hair care products for protecting hair fall, dandruff and baldness; facial treatments such as acne and freckles, removing wrinkles, fresh breath; body care treatments such as body grace. In last decades, women use cosmetics for health care, but recent studies show that men are also using cosmetics at an increasing rate. That is why the cosmetic industry can afford to spend millions of dollars a year on magazine and television advertisements for their new cosmetics^[3]. Practical implications – UAE community is encompassing different nationalities, resulting in a multicultural cultural values, attitudes & behaviors

towards cosmetics & products containing natural ingredients. Hence, a great effort is focused on marketing actions such as displaying and advertising which have been customized accordingly, to target women's attitudes, and approaches in terms of beauty especially the face^[4]. A Literature Review was made in order to provide a background to the method applied, with references to other papers and books related to this subject and to clarify the precise meaning of the terms used during this study. Attitude is an act as go-between women in such communities which influence their behavior towards these products. That has impact on consumption and rapid growth in the economic conditions^[5]. Attitudes can be defined widely as "an enduring organization of motivational, emotional, perceptual and cognitive processes with respect to some aspect of our environment"^[6]. More specifically, "attitude refers to knowledge and positive or negative feelings about an object or activity" or "overall evaluation that expresses how much we like or dislike an object, issue, person or action"^[7].

To the authors' knowledge, there no previous research has been conducted for UAE in this field. This paper demonstrates that it is important for the marketers to take into account multicultural and ethnic values while marketing to them^[8]

This study focuses on analysing emirates women attitudes in relation to several factors such as: level of education, situational factors and also personality variables such as age^[9]. Traditionally women use cosmetics for health care, but recent studies show that men are also using cosmetics at an increasing rate, which is increasing the future of cosmetic industries. With rising demand from men and women^[10], the market is getting more expanded and numerous competitors are emerging in this industry, and herbal care products are one of such players in this industry^[11]. In Sayma et al.'s (2008) study find that a number of plants are used to develop a herbal skin care product, and they may range from hard items such as seeds, fruits, barks, woods, leaves, roots, flowers, pollen to soft items such as coconut oil, milk, honey, salt, and water^[12].

The significance of herbal ingredients as healing agents and their role in beauty care is now widely recognized, and as a result, interests in exploitation of medical and aromatic as pharmaceuticals, herbal remedied, flavorings, perfumes, cosmetics and other natural products has been increasing for last few years^[13].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

The research methodology adopted for this study by analysis of a designed questionnaire. The questions of the questionnaire were selected according to literature review and to Justify for the suitability of the aim of the study.

1. Data collection

The data collection in this study was done by email or distribution by hand sending that was sent to the participants. Among the participants Dubai Pharmacy College (DPC) graduates whose email addresses were conveniently available Third year (76), Dubai Pharmacy College, UAE, participated, that helped in reaching women who would be eligible to participate in the study.. This was another reason for why I chose to conduct the data collection by sending the survey through email. In addition to customers in shopping centers & pharmacie^[1].

2. Data Analysis:

For data analysis Exel sheet was used and presented in figure and tables^[1].

RESULTS

1. Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Table 1. Age distribution of the research population

Age	Number of women
<19	12
20-35	102
36-39	33
40-60	15
60>	17

In the questionnaire, there were questions related to age, marital status, education, occupation and income in order

Table 2. Demographics of eligible respondents

Respondents	179	
Total (eligible)	150	
Marital Status	Percentage	
Non-married	110	73%
Married- no children	23	16%
Married- with children	17	11%
Education		
Secondary education or lower	39	22.9%
Universities of Applied Sciences	107	71.3%
Other Universities	4	2.6%
Income		
Without income (depend on husbands & parent)	89	54%
Under 10 000 AED	30	31%
10 000-20 000 AED	23	10%
Over 20 000 AED	1	5%
Occupational situation		
Studying	89	59.3%
Working	31	20.6%
Unemployed	30	20.1%

to learn about the demographics of the respondents. In the above table, the age distribution of the population is illustrated. These were the women who were selected to have the option to participate in this study. All together, 179 responses completed the questionnaire out of the 210. This response rate of 85.2% is a very good rate when compared to limited time of authors.

Among the 179 responses, there were 25 respondents who did not meet the required criteria for this research; these respondents were not taken into consideration. There were total of 150 eligible responses that were taken into account in this study. In the table 2 bellow, the demographics of the respondents are presented. Out of all the respondents around 40% belonged to the younger age due to participation of university students mostly in this study. The percentages have been calculated from the total number of all eligible respondents (150).

Information of the respondents

The survey Part 1 includes personal information of the respondent. Marital status, occupation, education, and the respondent's category according to the age.

Age -inclusion criteria: Young 20 -40 years of age; Old age people 40-60years of age.

a. Age of the participant

It was revealed from the survey that out of the total 210 respondents, only 150 satisfy the inclusion criteria. Among the total participants 60.1% were < 30 years of age, 28.3% of Middle age (30-40 years) and 11.6% were the old age > 40 years of age (Figure. 1).

b. Education level of the participants

The survey showed that out of the total 150 respondents' data from our survey, the participants having Pre-college level education were 29.2 %, College level were 63.2% and with no college education or having informal education were found to be 7.7%. (Figure 2).

c. Income of the participants

The respondents who are older age had overall greater income than women in the younger age. More than half of the working earned less than 10 000 AED per month, and only one respondents earned over 20 000 AED (Figure 3).

d. Marital Status

The majority of the younger women did married and the married not have children

The biggest difference in the demographics when comparing the two age categories

Questionnaire Data Analysis

Users and non-users of Cosmetics

On the query whether the participants used herbal cosmetics use, out of the total 150, 60.0% of participants are satisfied and 21.4 % somewhat satisfied (Figure 5.).

General interest

As seen in the figure 6, majorities of younger women and older women were either fairly or very interested in cosmetics. Almost every respondent in both age categories thought that skin care products were very interested, satisfied & very important. (Fig. 6-8).

All in all, it was found that all the respondents almost every respondent in both age categories women were either Very necessary or very interested in cosmetics (Fig. 5). Also, they are satisfied with their cosmetic products

Cosmetic make-up & skin care product's usage rate and application

The comparison of Cosmetic make-ups product's use

Figure 7- demonstrate skin care product's consumption, findings showed that women were concerned about sun protection creams as first important product, then day cream, night cream and moisturizing cream. Relating to the reasons of consuming they commented in order to maintain a healthy skin^[14].

The comparison of the skin care products' use

Table 3: Cosmetic skin care Products' Use Frequency Rate

Skin care Products	Frequency Rate
Facial foam/ Cleanser/ Toner	2.91
Day/ Night/ Moisturizing cream	4.78
Eye cream/ Anti wrinkle cream	2.26
Sun protection	5.22
Others	2.70

Table 4- Cosmetics Expenditure

0-100 EAD	100-300 EAD	300-600 EAD	>600 EAD
33%	27%	25%	15%

Cosmetics Expenditure per month

Table 5. The products range vs frequency of use

Usage Frequency	Hair Styling	Hair Color	Facial powder	Lip-gloss	Blush	Sun protection	Foundation	Eye shadow	Eye liner	Mascara
Never Use	16	18	26	36	33	7	10	20	10	5
Sometimes	48	40	40	45	50	43	36	56	58	15
Regular	36	42	35	29	27	37	54	24	32	80

In this research, the authors found that of women who use skin care products are students and the rest of them employers, employees & housewives. 60% of students who use skin care products spend only 0-300 per month and the rest of them (25%), (25%), (15%), spend around 301-600 and >600 EAD per month respectively.

Factors Influence on women' decision making of their cosmetics use

Influence of reference groups

Summary of the most influence person on women's selection behavior in table 6

Table 6. The most influence person on women's selection behavior

Persons	%
Yourself	5.52
Spouse/ Partner	2.30
Family	2.35
Friend/ Colleague	4.10
Expert	3.82
Sales representative	2.26
Presenter/ celebrity endorsement	2.13

As seen in the bellow figure 12, majorities of both younger women and older women were either very often or often influenced by their own selves or friends.

The majority of both groups 65 % of the younger and the older women reported that their buying decisions are affected by themselves then friends and advertisements, while married one by their spouses.

Concerning marketing communication, Personal selling recommendation, price, brand, ingredients or product attributes. None of the younger women said their purchase behaviour in terms of facial skin care products is affected by opinions of a sales person at a store or a beauty professional. But affected in the order by quality, ingredients, ingredients, price then promotion^[15]

Information Source

As seen in the figures 10 when women have been asked from which of the sources do you in general get information before purchasing a facial skin care product. Approximately half of both groups (54,2% of the younger and 46,3% of the older women) look for information from products' manufacturers' websites. A little over a third (33,3% of the young and 41,8% of old age category) turned to the sales personnel at a store to get information before buying a product^[16].

Purchase locations:

As seen in the figure 11, approximately half of both groups (54,2% of the younger and 46,3% of the older women) look for information before making a decision on which

facial skin care product to purchase from products' manufacturers' websites. A little over a third (33,3% of the young and 41,8% of old age category) turned to the sales personnel at a store to get information before buying a product.

Table 7: Products attribute Influence on women' decision making of their cosmetics use

Factors	%
Price	5.10
Brand	3.48
Organoleptic properties (fragrance & color)	3.26
Ingredient	3.61
Promotion and advertising	4.74
Packaging	3.43
Store location	3.26

Factors influencing women 'attitudes to use cosmetic make-up products

Result showed Price & marketing communication (Promotion and advertising) are the most important factors that influence women using cosmetics & skin care products.

Reasons to use or not use skin care products, using the products

Reasons to use skin care products, using the products

Summary of the reasons to use skin care products, using the products in Table 6.

Table 8: Reasons for using the skin care products

For Medical Reasons	2.78
For personal hygiene	4.78
for improving the skin	4.87
for self esteem	3.22
for attractiveness	4.3
Other	3.74

Factors influencing women 'attitudes not to use cosmetic skin care products

Table 9: Factors influencing women 'attitudes not to use cosmetic skin care products

Skin care products	%
Price	5.27
Brand	2.69
Quality/attribute of product	2.96
Ingredient	2.73
Promotion and advertising	2.62
Packaging	2.08
Store location	3.52

Evaluative criteria between different alternatives for choosing a product:

Related to evaluating and choosing between different alternatives^[17], the participants were asked to select three most important factors regarding the kind of evaluative criteria they use to make distinctions between different

alternatives i.e. the determining factors in selecting a product. Below are illustrative figure of the responses of both young and middle-aged women^[18].

Skin care products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives:

Table 10: Summary of the products and alternative percentages

Skin care products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives	
Affordability of the product	39.2
The suitability of the product for one's own skin	56.3
Previous usage experiences	53.4
Naturalness	9.6
Consistency	15.7
Brand	21.2
Quality	60.5

Make-up products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives:

Table 11: Summary of make-up products between different alternatives

Make-up products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives:	
Affordability of the product	32.4
The suitability of the product for one's own skin	66.2
Previous usage experiences	45.7
Naturalness	20.7
Consistency	26.4
Brand	25.6
Quality	50.1

Daily use facial skin care products preferences:

Facial skin care habits and preferences

The majority of all the respondents in this study reported that they use facial cream (82,5%), facial cleanser (73,5%), facial toner (60,5%), and eye cream (54,2%) of the facial skin care products recommended for daily use. In addition to, (31.1%) of the women they use also firming facial cream.

Half (49,5%) of the women also reported that they use eye make-up remover. When asked about what kind of facial cream the respondents used, the majority of all women said they use moisturizing facial cream (75,4%). However, over a half (45,4%) of the moisturizing cream they use day facial cream^[19].

Approximately 60% of women commented using both day and night creams separately and also half (51,8%) reported that they use both day and night creams for their facial skin. However, the rest of the two age groups reported that they do not use both day and night creams. The most common reasons for not using both were that it is too expensive to use both or that they feel that one cream is simply enough. Many also reported that night creams tend to be too heavy and that is why only day cream is used^[20].

Table 12: Summary of The recommended facial skin care products for daily use, habits and preferences

Skin care products	
Facial cream	82.5%
Moisturizing facial cream	75.4%
Day creams	45.4%
Night creams	30%
Facial cleanser	73.5%
Facial toner	60.5%
Eye cream	54.2%
Eye make-up remover	49.5%
Firming facial cream	30.1%

The majority of all the respondents in this study reported that they use facial cream (88,5%), facial cleanser (83,5%),

facial toner (62,6%), and eye cream (61,2%) of the facial skin care products recommended for daily use. Half (47, 5%) of the women also reported that they use eye make-up remover. When asked about what kind of facial cream the respondents used, the majority of all women said they use moisturizing facial cream (69,6%). However, over a third (36,3%) of the older women reported they use also firming facial cream [21].

Approximately 60% of 40-60 year-old women used both day and night creams separately and also half (51,8%) of the younger women reported that they use both day and night creams for their facial skin[22]. However, the rest of the two age groups reported that they do not use both day and night creams. The most common reasons for not using both were that it is too expensive to use both or that they feel that one cream is simply enough. Many also reported

Figure. 1: Age group of participants

Figure 2: Participants education level

Figure 3: Participants Income

Figure 4. Participants Marital Status

Figure 5. Users and non-users of herbal cosmetics among the participants

Figure 6. Interest towards and necessity of facial skin care products

Figure 7- skin care products' satisfaction

Figure 8- Importance Level of Cosmetics in Life

Fig.9 Cosmetic Make-Up Products' Usage Frequency Rate

Figure 10: comparison of Skin care product's use

Fig. 11- Cosmetics Expenditure

Figure 12: The most influence person on women's purchasing behavior

that night creams tend to be too heavy and that is why only day cream is used.

Even greater differences in the attitudes towards the use of natural ingredients in facial skin care products can be seen when comparing the beliefs of women who reported to be very interested in cosmetics and taking care of their beauty to the beliefs of women who said they are not very interested. A mere fifth (18,2%) of the women who were not very interested in cosmetics believe that products consisting of natural ingredients are better for facial skin than products which do not contain natural ingredients [23].

Daily Routines of Cosmetics Use Rate, Frequency & Time Application:

In contrast, over half (56,5%) of those women who were very interested in cosmetics and taking care of their beauty believed that natural ingredients in facial skin care products make the products better. The difference can also be seen among those women who thought that products made of natural ingredients are not any better than products which do not contain ingredients from nature; this view was shared by more than a third (36,4%) of women who were not very interested in cosmetics but only by a

Figure 13. The sources of the Information

Figure 14. Purchase locations

Figure 15: Products attribute Influence on women' decision making of their cosmetics use

Figure 16: Reasons for using the skin care products

Figure 17: Factors affecting women not to use cosmetic skin care products

Figure 18: Skin care products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives

few (6,5%) women who were interested in cosmetics. See appendix 5 for frequencies.

Effect on buying behaviour

This section of this thesis discusses how the attitudes towards and the beliefs about natural ingredients affect purchasing behaviour. Figure 14. Willingness to pay more for products containing natural ingredients compared to believing in the superiority of natural ingredients^[24]

Women adoption of herbal therapies is influenced by demographic attributes, friends were found to play a dominant role as a communication mode (word-of-mouth), herbal professionals & advertisement^[25].

The study found that increased beauty consciousness tied with increasing income, products characteristics & media communication channels, contributed to increasing women using rate of beauty & skin care products.

Although a grocery store was a common source for common use items including cosmetics, it was not found to have associated with cosmetics products purchase^[26].

The study revealed that housewives with low educated level are influenced in using beauty & skin care products by primary benefit such as price, quality & quantity. In contrast to that^[27,28], findings showed that educated working women are influenced by secondary benefit such

Figure 19: Make-up products Evaluative criteria between different alternatives

Figure 20: The recommended facial skin care products for daily use, habits and preferences.

Figure 21: The comparison of the skin care product's use preference

as ingredients of the product, the purpose of the product, innovative features, manufacturer 'reputation, and certification of the product [29].

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to explore the factors that contribute to form women attitudes & motives towards cosmetics[30,31], and to determine the relationships among demographic attributes, age, gender, level of education, marital status and using motives in beauty & skin care products in UAE.

Figure 22: Comparison between Cosmetic make-up products use preference

Although this study has several contributions[32], this study has several limitations as well. First the study used a small sample mostly students of different universities located in Fujairah & Dubai, UAE, and confined the scope to limited districts in UAE [33]. Second, this study doesn't attempt to generalize its findings. Therefore, future study can also need to investigate the differences in findings especially in age groups, generations, sex, urban-rural and educated and semi/uneducated cosmetics & skin care users[34], to provide important insights, in this context[35,36].

Figure 23: Interest towards herbal cosmetics and skin care products

Figure 24: Routines of herbal Cosmetics Use

REFERENCES

- Hawkins, Del I., Best, R. J., Coney, K. A., Consumer Behaviour: Building Market Strategy. McGraw-Hill/Irwin. 9th Ed. 2004.
- Petty, R. E., Unnava, H. R., Strathman, A.J., Theories of attitude change, Handbook of consumer Behaviour, Prentice-hall. 1991.
- Hoyer, W.D., MacInnis, D.J, Consumer Behaviour, Houghton Mifflin Company. 2nd Ed. 2001.
- Antoinette A. (2005), Drug Store News, beauty care: *Stay-young trend spills over to men, as boy boomers boost skin care sales*, November 21, 2005, pp.33-34
- Antoinette A. (2007), Drug Store News: *Men's grooming gains social acceptance*, November 12, pp 66
- Antoinette A. (2009), Drug Store News, beauty care: *Opportunity remains in men's grooming*, April 20, 2009, pp.117
- Askegaard S., Banossy G. & Solomon M. (1999a), consumer behavior: *An introduction to consumer behavior*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc.
- Askegaard S., Banossy G. & Solomon M. (1999b), consumer behavior: *Individual decisionmaking*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc.

9. Barel, O., Paye, M. & Maibach I (2001), *Handbook of cosmetic science and technology*, (eds.) New York: Informa Health Care.
10. Blanchin, A., Chareyron, C. & Levert, Q. (2007), *The customer behavior in the men's cosmetics market*, School of Business and Engineering, University of Halmstad.
11. Brown, I.R. (2006), *Mastering marketing: a comprehensive introduction to the skills of developing and defending your company's revenue*, (2 ed.), Thorogood Publishing, pp 204-208
12. Bryman, A. & Bell, E (2007). *Business Research Methods: Second Edition*. Oxford University press: New York.
13. Borden, N (1964), *The concept of the marketing mix*, Journal of Advertising Research.
14. Cheng, S.O., Ding, H.T. & Fan, S.C. (2010), Factors Affecting Consumption Behavior Of Metrosexual Toward Male Grooming Products, Vol.6, No.1 February 2010, Pp. 574- 590
15. Christopher, S. T., Piaw, T. C. & Kee, W. K. (2007), Supply chain analysis: *a handbook on the interaction of information, system and optimization*, Volume 119 of International series in operations research & management science, pp 14-22
16. Clifton, R., Simmons, J. & Ahmad, S. (2004), *The economist series: Brands and branding*, (2 ed.), Bloomberg Press, New Jersey
17. Coad, D. (2008), *The metrosexual: gender, sexuality, and sport*, Volume 283 of SUNY series on sport, culture, and social relations, New York: SUNY Press
18. Cole, L. (2008), "Male grooming grows up", *ICIS chemical business*", vol. 273, no. 14, pp. 36-37. A Study of Factors Affecting on Men's Skin Care Products Purchasing Page 58 of 77
19. Conseur A. A. (2004), *Factors influencing the emergence of the metrosexual*. Dean of the Graduate School, University of Georgia
20. Dalgic, T. (2006), *Handbook of niche marketing: principles and practice: Haworth Series in Segmented, Targeted, and Customized Market*, Binghamton: Routledge
21. Data panel (2002), *Europe*, TGI Europa.
22. Desborder, E.T. & Kimmel, A. (2002), *Sexe, genre et marketing, définition des concepts et analyse de la littérature*, Décisions marketing, no. 26, p.65
23. Elsey B. & Sukato N. (2009), *ABAC Journal: A model of male consumer behavior in buying skin care products in Thailand*, Vol. 29, No. 1, pp.39-52
24. Feng, W. (2008), *Male Cosmetics Advertisements in Chinese and U.S. Men's Lifestyle Magazine*, Diss. Ohio: the Scripps College of Communication, Ohio University.
25. Firat, A. F. (1994), "Gender and Consumption: Transcending the Feminine?" in *Gender Issues in Consumer Behavior*, ed. Janeen Arnold Costa, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 205-28
26. Flak, J. (2009), *Starting Point: Men are men*, GCI magazine of November 2009, pp 4
27. Hirschey, M. (2009), *Fundamentals of Managerial Economics*, (9 ed.), Cengage Learning, pp 565
28. Hofstede G. (1991), *culture and organization: she, he and s(he)*. London: arperCollins.
29. Janowska K. (2008), *Metrosexuals men's shopping habits – study of modern men's clothing brand selection*.
30. Julie, C.V. & Michael, W. (2002), *Differences in purchase behavior between France and the USA: the cosmetic industry*, Journal of Fashion marketing and Management:, Vol.6, No. 4, pp 396-407
31. Joppe, M. (2000). *The Research Process*. Retrieved February 25, 1998
32. Kimmel S, M. & Aronson, A. (2004), *Men and Masculinities: A-J*, Volume 1 of *Men and Masculinities: A Social, Cultural, and Historical Encyclopedia*, California: ABCCLIO
33. Kotler, P. (2000), *Marketing Management*, (10 ed.), Prentice Hall, pp 505
34. Lamb, C.W., Hair, J.F. & McDaniel, C. (2008), *Essential of Marketing*, (6 ed.), Cengage Learning, pp 337-338
35. Lennard, C. (2009), *Market Report: Men's Care*, GCI magazine of November 2009, pp 23- 25. A Study of Factors Affecting on Men's Skin Care Products Purchasing Page 59 of 77
36. Lynch M., Spencer J. S. & Steele M. C. (1993), *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, Self-image Resilience and Dissonance: The Role of Affirmational Resources*, Vol. 64, No. 6, pp. 885-896.
37. L'Oréal Report (2010), *The L'Oréal UK Min's Grooming Report*, March 2010
38. Imogen M. (2005), *Men's Grooming: Brands Drive Growth*, GCI magazine of February 2005, pp 39-40
39. Sturrock, F & Pioch, E (1998), 'Making himself attractive: the growing consumption of grooming products', *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 337-343.